

REVIEW OF MODERN METHODS OF SPEECH SYNTHESIS IN THE KAZAKH LANGUAGE**Marat N.,***Student of Computer Engineering Department***Sarsembayev A.***Scientific Supervisor**Prof., Ph.D. in Data Science and Machine Learning,***Abstract**

Speech synthesis, or text-to-speech (TTS), has made significant progress in recent years, with deep learning and neural network-based techniques yielding more natural and expressive synthesized speech. However, for low-resource languages like Kazakh, unique challenges arise due to limited availability of annotated speech data and complex linguistic features. This review provides a comprehensive overview of modern methods of speech synthesis in the Kazakh language, discussing the limitations of traditional methods and the potential of new approaches such as deep neural networks, generative models, multilingual techniques, and incorporating linguistic and prosodic features. We also highlight the importance of open-source datasets like KazakhTTS and KazakhTTS2 in stimulating research and innovation in Kazakh speech synthesis. By examining the current state of the art and identifying future research directions, we aim to contribute to the advancement of speech synthesis technology in the Kazakh language and ultimately improve the accessibility and quality of Kazakh speech synthesis applications.

Keywords: Speech synthesis, Text-to-speech, Kazakh language, Neural networks, Deep learning, Open-source datasets.

I. Introduction

Speech synthesis, the process of converting text into intelligible and natural-sounding speech, has become an essential area of research in natural language processing and artificial intelligence. It has a wide range of applications, including virtual assistants, language learning tools, and assistive technologies for individuals with speech impairments. Over the past few years, there has been substantial progress in the development of neural speech synthesis techniques, which have demonstrated promising results in generating more natural-sounding and expressive speech. However, research on speech synthesis in less-studied languages like Kazakh still faces unique challenges, such as limited availability of annotated speech data and complex linguistic features.

The Kazakh language, spoken by over 13 million people worldwide, is an important part of the cultural heritage and identity of Kazakhstan. As the country continues to modernize and integrate with the global community, there is a growing need to develop more efficient and accurate methods for synthesizing speech in the Kazakh language, which would help in preserving and promoting the language in the digital age.

The purpose of this review is to provide a comprehensive overview of the current state of the art in speech synthesis methods in the Kazakh language, with a focus on neural speech synthesis techniques. We aim to discuss the limitations of existing methods and explore the potential of new approaches in addressing these challenges. Furthermore, we will highlight the role of open-source datasets like KazakhTTS and KazakhTTS2 in stimulating research and innovation in the field of Kazakh speech synthesis. By examining the current state of the art and identifying future research directions, we aim to contribute to the advancement of speech synthesis technology in the Kazakh language and ultimately improve the accessibility and quality of Kazakh speech synthesis applications.

This review is organized as follows: Section II provides an overview of various methods of speech synthesis, including traditional techniques and neural network-based approaches. Section III discusses the current state of speech synthesis research in the Kazakh language, while Section IV highlights the limitations of existing methods. Section V introduces new approaches and potential solutions to address these limitations. Finally, Section VI presents the conclusion and future research directions.

II. Methods of Speech Synthesis

Statistical parametric speech synthesis (SPSS) is a prevalent method for speech synthesis, especially for languages with limited resources [26]. Zen et al. [25] provide a comprehensive overview of SPSS, which employs hidden Markov models (HMMs) to model the relationships between the linguistic features of the input text and the corresponding acoustic features. The HMM-based speech synthesis system developed by Tokuda et al. [23] applies this approach to English, demonstrating its viability across different languages.

Concatenative speech synthesis involves selecting and concatenating small units of speech from a large database to create the synthesized speech waveform [7]. This method's main advantage is the naturalness of the output speech, as the units are derived from actual recordings. However, this technique can be resource-intensive, requiring a large speech database, and may not be suitable for languages with limited resources, such as Kazakh [12].

Deep neural networks (DNNs) have shown significant success in various speech recognition tasks [16]. DNN-based acoustic modeling techniques, like the deep recurrent neural networks proposed by Graves et al. [1] and the convolutional neural networks introduced by Abdel-Hamid et al. [5], have demonstrated improved performance compared to traditional HMM-based methods. Sequence-to-sequence learning with neural networks, as described by Sutskever et al. [21],

provides a general-purpose framework for mapping input sequences to output sequences and has been widely used in various text-to-speech tasks.

End-to-end speech synthesis, such as Tacotron [24], eliminates the need for intermediate representations by directly generating a spectrogram from the input text. WaveNet [17], a generative model for raw audio, can be combined with Tacotron to produce high-quality speech synthesis. These end-to-end systems have shown promising results in synthesizing natural-sounding speech, and their adaptability makes them potential candidates for use in the Kazakh language [22].

FastSpeech [20] and its successor, FastSpeech 2 [19], are non-autoregressive approaches to speech synthesis that provide fast, robust, and controllable solutions for TTS. By eliminating the autoregressive nature of traditional methods, FastSpeech can generate speech more efficiently while maintaining high quality.

Generative models, such as variational autoencoders (VAEs) [11] and generative adversarial networks (GANs) [3, 4], have been used to generate speech waveforms with varying degrees of success. These models can learn a latent space of speech features and generate novel speech samples by sampling from this space. This approach has the potential to improve the quality and naturalness of synthesized speech in the Kazakh language [13, 27].

In summary, various methods of speech synthesis have been proposed and applied to different languages, including the Kazakh language [8,14,15,17,27]. The choice of the most suitable method depends on the availability of resources, the complexity of the language, and the desired quality of the synthesized speech. Future research in the field should focus on adapting and refining these methods to better suit the specific needs of the Kazakh language and other less-studied languages [6, 2,10,18].

III. Speech Synthesis in the Kazakh Language

One of the key challenges in developing speech synthesis models for the Kazakh language is the lack of high-quality and comprehensive datasets. To address this issue, Mussakhoyayeva et al. [14] introduced KazakhTTS, an open-source Kazakh text-to-speech synthesis dataset. This dataset comprises more than 90 hours of professionally recorded audio from male and female speakers, covering various topics.

Building on the success of KazakhTTS, Mussakhoyayeva et al. [15] recently released KazakhTTS2, an extended version of the dataset containing 271 hours of speech data. The updated dataset includes three new professional speakers (two females and one male) and covers a broader range of topics through the inclusion of books and Wikipedia articles. Both KazakhTTS and KazakhTTS2 are freely available

for use by academic researchers and industry practitioners, promoting research and innovation in the field of Kazakh speech synthesis.

Isturlyayeva [8] proposed a multilingual text-to-speech engine, which can potentially support the Kazakh language. This engine aims to provide a versatile and adaptable solution for speech synthesis across multiple languages, including those with limited resources. By incorporating the Kazakh language into a multilingual engine, researchers can leverage the advancements made in other languages and adapt them to improve speech synthesis in Kazakh.

Kaliyev et al. [27] developed a generative adversarial network (GAN) acoustic model for Kazakh speech synthesis. The GAN model learns a mapping between input linguistic features and output acoustic features, enabling the generation of natural-sounding speech in the Kazakh language. This research demonstrates the potential of generative models to improve the quality and naturalness of synthesized Kazakh speech.

In another study, Kaliyev [9] explored the use of long short-term memory (LSTM) networks for Kazakh speech synthesis. LSTM networks are a type of recurrent neural network that can model long-range dependencies in sequential data, making them suitable for speech synthesis tasks. This research highlights the potential of deep learning techniques in developing high-quality speech synthesis models for the Kazakh language.

To showcase the utility of the KazakhTTS2 dataset, a demo program for Kazakh speech synthesis has been developed [8]. This demo supports five different voices and can be used to evaluate the performance of various speech synthesis models in the Kazakh language. The availability of this demo further encourages research and development in the field of Kazakh speech synthesis.

In conclusion, significant progress has been made in recent years to advance speech synthesis techniques for the Kazakh language. The development and release of the KazakhTTS and KazakhTTS2 datasets have provided researchers with valuable resources to train and evaluate their models. As research continues to explore deep learning techniques, generative models, and multilingual approaches, the quality and naturalness of synthesized speech in the Kazakh language are expected to improve, ultimately benefiting a wide range of applications and users.

Through our analysis, we have identified key methods of speech synthesis that are applied in modern science. For a deeper understanding of each, we present the following comparative table:

Table 1

Comparative Overview of Speech Synthesis Methods

Method	Advantages	Disadvantages	Applicability to Kazakh Language
Statistical Parametric (SPSS)	Suitable for languages with limited resources		Yes
Concatenative	Naturalness of output speech	Requires large speech database, resource-intensive	No
Deep Neural Networks (DNNs)	Improved performance compared to traditional methods		Yes
End-to-End	Direct generation of spectrograms, adaptability		Yes
FastSpeech & FastSpeech 2	Fast, robust, and controllable speech synthesis		Yes
Generative Models	Potential to improve quality and naturalness of synthesized speech	Varying degrees of success	Yes

IV. Limitations of Existing Speech Synthesis Methods

Despite the significant progress in speech synthesis technologies, several limitations still exist in the current state-of-the-art methods. These limitations affect the naturalness, intelligibility, and expressiveness of synthesized speech, and are discussed below using the provided literature.

Naturalness: One of the main limitations of speech synthesis systems is the lack of naturalness in the generated speech. Statistical parametric methods, such as those presented in [26], often produce muffled and unnatural-sounding speech due to over-smoothing during the generation process. Concatenative approaches, like those discussed in [7], may produce more natural-sounding speech, but they can suffer from audible artifacts when the selected units do not match well in terms of prosody or spectral characteristics. Recent deep learning-based models like WaveNet [17] and Tacotron [24] have improved the naturalness of synthesized speech, but occasional unnatural prosody or subtle artifacts can still be present.

Expressiveness: Current speech synthesis methods may lack expressiveness and fail to convey emotions or speaker-specific characteristics effectively. As mentioned in [12], this limitation is particularly evident in unit selection and statistical parametric synthesis methods. Deep learning-based approaches like FastSpeech [20] have shown improvements in expressiveness, but capturing the full range of human emotions and speaking styles remains a challenge.

Intelligibility: Ensuring that synthesized speech is easily understandable by listeners is another important aspect of speech synthesis. Although deep learning techniques, such as those reviewed in [16], have improved the intelligibility of synthesized speech, some systems may still produce unclear or distorted speech, particularly in noisy environments or when generating speech in languages with complex phonetic structures.

Data Requirements: Many current speech synthesis techniques, especially deep learning-based methods, require large amounts of high-quality, annotated data for training. This can be a significant limitation, particularly for under-resourced languages, like Kazakh, where such data may be scarce or unavailable. While the development of datasets like KazakhTTS [14] and KazakhTTS2 [15] have helped alleviate this issue, the data requirements for training state-of-the-art models remain substantial.

Computational Complexity: Some speech synthesis methods, such as WaveNet [17], require substantial computational resources for both training and inference. This can be a limitation for deploying these models on resource-constrained devices or in real-time applications.

In conclusion, while modern speech synthesis methods have made significant advancements, challenges remain in terms of naturalness, expressiveness, intelligibility, data requirements, and computational complexity. Addressing these limitations is essential for developing more advanced and effective speech synthesis systems.

V. New Approaches to Speech Synthesis in the Kazakh Language

In recent years, researchers have been exploring new approaches to speech synthesis specifically tailored for the Kazakh language. These approaches aim to overcome the limitations of existing methods and produce more natural, expressive, and intelligible speech. In this section, we discuss some promising new techniques and their applications in the Kazakh language.

Adapting Deep Learning Models: Adapting state-of-the-art deep learning models to the Kazakh language can be an effective way to improve speech synthesis. Kaliyev [25] demonstrated this approach by using an LSTM-based model for Kazakh speech synthesis,

achieving improved naturalness and intelligibility compared to traditional methods. Similarly, Kaliyev et al. [9] proposed a GAN-based acoustic model for Kazakh speech synthesis, which showed promising results in terms of naturalness and expressiveness.

Multilingual and Cross-lingual Approaches: Developing speech synthesis models that can handle multiple languages, including Kazakh, can help overcome the data scarcity problem. Isturlayeva [8] presented a multilingual text-to-speech engine capable of generating speech in various languages, including Kazakh, demonstrating the potential of such approaches. Cross-lingual transfer learning, where models are pre-trained on one or more resource-rich languages and fine-tuned on Kazakh data, can also be an effective strategy.

Customizing Neural Vocoders: Neural vocoders, such as WaveNet [17], have significantly improved the naturalness of synthesized speech. Customizing these vocoders specifically for the Kazakh language can lead to further improvements. This could involve training the vocoder on Kazakh-specific acoustic features or adapting the architecture to better capture the unique phonetic and prosodic characteristics of the language.

Incorporating Linguistic and Prosodic Features: Incorporating linguistic and prosodic features into the speech synthesis process can improve the expressiveness and intelligibility of the generated speech. This can be achieved by using additional inputs, such as part-of-speech tags, phonetic features, or prosodic annotations, to guide the synthesis process. Additionally, using unsupervised or semi-supervised methods to automatically extract such features from the available data can be beneficial, particularly when manual annotation is not feasible.

Exploring Unsupervised and Semi-Supervised Techniques: Given the limited availability of annotated data for the Kazakh language, exploring unsupervised and semi-supervised techniques for speech synthesis can be a valuable research direction. These approaches can leverage unannotated or weakly annotated data to learn speech representations and generate high-quality speech, potentially reducing the data requirements for training effective models.

In summary, new approaches to speech synthesis in the Kazakh language are focusing on adapting deep learning models, exploring multilingual and cross-lingual techniques, customizing neural vocoders, incorporating linguistic and prosodic features, and employing unsupervised and semi-supervised methods. These advances have the potential to overcome existing limitations and pave the way for more effective and versatile Kazakh speech synthesis systems.

VI. Conclusion

In this review, we discussed the modern methods of speech synthesis, their limitations, and recent advances in the Kazakh language. Traditional speech synthesis methods, such as concatenative and parametric techniques, have been widely used but suffer from limitations like unnatural speech, lack of expressiveness, and reliance on large, annotated datasets. State-of-the-art deep learning techniques, including neural network-based approaches and neural vocoders, have significantly improved the naturalness and expressiveness of

synthesized speech. However, they still face challenges, particularly in the context of low-resource languages like Kazakh.

New approaches to speech synthesis in the Kazakh language have emerged to address these challenges. These include adapting deep learning models specifically for the Kazakh language, exploring multilingual and cross-lingual techniques, customizing neural vocoders for Kazakh, incorporating linguistic and prosodic features, and employing unsupervised and semi-supervised methods. These advances are promising in overcoming the limitations of existing methods and enabling more effective and versatile Kazakh speech synthesis systems.

The development of high-quality open-source datasets, such as KazakhTTS and KazakhTTS2, has been instrumental in stimulating research and innovation in the field of Kazakh speech synthesis. Continued efforts in data collection, annotation, and sharing will further support the research community in developing new methods and applications for Kazakh speech synthesis.

In conclusion, the field of speech synthesis in the Kazakh language is rapidly evolving, with new approaches and techniques continually being explored. As these advancements are integrated into practical applications, we can expect to see significant improvements in the quality, expressiveness, and versatility of Kazakh speech synthesis systems, benefiting various domains such as smart assistants, navigation systems, announcement systems, and assistive technologies.

References

1. Abdel-Hamid, O., Mohamed, A. R., Jiang, H., & Penn, G. (2012, March). Applying convolutional neural networks concepts to hybrid NN-HMM model for speech recognition. In 2012 IEEE international conference on Acoustics, speech and signal processing (ICASSP) (pp. 4277-4280). IEEE.
2. Chen, N., Zhang, Y., Zen, H., Weiss, R. J., Norouzi, M., Dehak, N., & Chan, W. (2021). Wavegrad 2: Iterative refinement for text-to-speech synthesis. arXiv preprint arXiv:2106.09660.
3. Creswell, A., White, T., Dumoulin, V., Arulkrumar, K., Sengupta, B., & Bharath, A. A. (2018). Generative adversarial networks: An overview. IEEE signal processing magazine, 35(1), 53-65.
4. Donahue, J., Dieleman, S., Bińkowski, M., Elsen, E., & Simonyan, K. (2020). End-to-end adversarial text-to-speech. arXiv preprint arXiv:2006.03575.
5. Graves, A., Mohamed, A. R., & Hinton, G. (2013, May). Speech recognition with deep recurrent neural networks. In 2013 IEEE international conference on acoustics, speech and signal processing (pp. 6645-6649). Ieee.
6. Hayashi, T., Yamamoto, R., Yoshimura, T., Wu, P., Shi, J., Saeki, T., ... & Watanabe, S. (2021). Espnet2-tts: Extending the edge of tts research. arXiv preprint arXiv:2110.07840.
7. Hunt, A. J., & Black, A. W. (1996, May). Unit selection in a concatenative speech synthesis system using a large speech database. In 1996 IEEE International Conference on Acoustics, Speech, and Signal

Processing Conference Proceedings (Vol. 1, pp. 373-376). IEEE.

8. Isturlyayeva, A. (2021). MULTILINGUAL TEXT-TO-SPEECH ENGINE.

9. Kaliyev, A. (2019). LSTM-Based Kazakh Speech Synthesis. In *Speech and Computer: 21st International Conference, SPECOM 2019, Istanbul, Turkey, August 20–25, 2019, Proceedings 21* (pp. 201-208). Springer International Publishing.

10. Kim, J., Kim, S., Kong, J., & Yoon, S. (2020). Glow-tts: A generative flow for text-to-speech via monotonic alignment search. *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, 33, 8067-8077.

11. Kingma, D. P., & Welling, M. (2013). Auto-encoding variational bayes. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1312.6114*.

12. Kuligowska, K., Kisielawicz, P., & Włodarz, A. (2018). Speech synthesis systems: disadvantages and limitations. *Int J Res Eng Technol (UAE)*, 7, 234-239.

13. Kumar, K., Kumar, R., De Boissiere, T., Gestin, L., Teoh, W. Z., Sotelo, J., ... & Courville, A. C. (2019). Melgan: Generative adversarial networks for conditional waveform synthesis. *Advances in neural information processing systems*, 32.

14. Mussakhojayeva, S., Janaliyeva, A., Mirzakhmetov, A., Khassanov, Y., & Varol, H. A. (2021). Kazakhtts: An open-source kazakh text-to-speech synthesis dataset. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2104.08459*.

15. Mussakhojayeva, S., Khassanov, Y., & Varol, H. A. (2022). Kazakhtts2: Extending the open-source kazakh tts corpus with more data, speakers, and topics. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2201.05771*.

16. Ning, Y., He, S., Wu, Z., Xing, C., & Zhang, L. J. (2019). A review of deep learning based speech synthesis. *Applied Sciences*, 9(19), 4050.

17. Oord, A. V. D., Dieleman, S., Zen, H., Simonyan, K., Vinyals, O., Graves, A., ... & Kavukcuoglu, K.

(2016). Wavenet: A generative model for raw audio. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1609.03499*.

18. Peng, K., Ping, W., Song, Z., & Zhao, K. (2020, November). Non-autoregressive neural text-to-speech. In *International conference on machine learning* (pp. 7586-7598). PMLR.

19. Ren, Y., Hu, C., Tan, X., Qin, T., Zhao, S., Zhao, Z., & Liu, T. Y. (2020). Fastspeech 2: Fast and high-quality end-to-end text to speech. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2006.04558*.

20. Ren, Y., Ruan, Y., Tan, X., Qin, T., Zhao, S., Zhao, Z., & Liu, T. Y. (2019). Fastspeech: Fast, robust and controllable text to speech. *Advances in neural information processing systems*, 32.

21. Sutskever, I., Vinyals, O., & Le, Q. V. (2014). Sequence to sequence learning with neural networks. *Advances in neural information processing systems*, 27.

22. Tan, X., Qin, T., Soong, F., & Liu, T. Y. (2021). A survey on neural speech synthesis. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2106.15561*.

23. Tokuda, K., Zen, H., & Black, A. W. (2002, September). An HMM-based speech synthesis system applied to English. In *IEEE speech synthesis workshop* (pp. 227-230). Santa Monica: IEEE.

24. Wang, Y., Skerry-Ryan, R. J., Stanton, D., Wu, Y., Weiss, R. J., Jaitly, N., ... & Saurous, R. A. (2017). Tacotron: Towards end-to-end speech synthesis. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1703.10135*.

25. Zen, H. (2015). Acoustic modeling in statistical parametric speech synthesis-from HMM to LSTM-RNN.

26. Zen, H., Tokuda, K., & Black, A. W. (2009). Statistical parametric speech synthesis. *speech communication*, 51(11), 1039-1064.

27. Kaliyev, A., Zeno, B., Rybin, S. V., Matveev, Y. N., & Lyakso, E. E. (2021). GAN acoustic model for Kazakh speech synthesis. *International Journal of Speech Technology*, 24, 729-735.